

Notas breves

A new species of *Scissurella* (Gastropoda, Scissurellidae) from Cuba

Una nueva especie de *Scissurella* (Gastropoda, Scissurellidae) de Cuba

Raúl FERNÁNDEZ GARCÉS*, Daniel L. GEIGER**, Emilio ROLÁN***
& Ángel A. LUQUE****

Recibido el 10-IV-2021. Aceptado el 21-V-2021

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:7EE440C7-3EF3-408F-A2A0-27870C4972A0

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, *Scissurella*, new species, Cuba.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Moluscos, *Scissurella*, nueva especie, Cuba.

INTRODUCTION

The bathyal molluscs are still poorly known in Cuba, and most of the records listed by ESPINOSA, FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS & ROLÁN (1995) and ESPINOSA (2006) come from old expeditions of the late 19th century and the first half of the 20th century. During the most recent 2017 cruise WB0517 of the R/V WEATHERBIRD II (Florida Institute of Oceanography) a systematic sampling of bathyal bottoms of the northwestern margin of Cuba was carried out for the first time, which permitted to document its diversity and to contribute to the establishment of an environmental baseline of the Gulf of Mexico. The studied area forms the Cuban

portion of the Gulf of Mexico and hosts part of the most diverse marine ecosystems of the Cuban archipelago.

The study of samples collected in that campaign yielded several new gastropod species of the genera *Brookula*, *Neusas*, *Emiliotia*, *Adeuomphalus*, *Ventsia*, and *Lyocyclus* (FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS, RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2018a, b, 2019a, b, c, d) and a preliminary list of 129 identified molluscan species (ARMENTEROS, 2019).

The family Scissurellidae was reviewed at global level by GEIGER (2012), who considered 33 valid living species of the genus *Scissurella*, of which seven live in the Atlantic Ocean and

* Centro de Estudios Ambientales de Cienfuegos (CEAC), Calle 17, esquina Ave. 46, Cienfuegos, Cuba, rfg44@nauta.cu

** Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History, 2559 Puesta del Sol, Santa Barbara, CA 93105, USA, dgeiger@sbnature2.org

*** Cánovas del Castillo, 22, 36202 Vigo (Pontevedra), España, emiliorolan@gmail.com

**** Centro de Investigación en Biodiversidad y Cambio Global (CIBC-UAM), Universidad Autónoma, C/Darwin 2, 28049 Madrid, España, angel.luque@inv.uam.es

only one, *Scissurella redferni* (Rolán, 1996), is known from the NW Atlantic (Caribbean) and Cuba. The present paper describes a new species of the genus *Scissurella* found in bathyal samples taken during the above mentioned WEATHERBIRD II cruise in 2017.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The cruise WB0517 of the R/V WEATHERBIRD II was carried out within the framework of the collaboration between the University of South Florida (USF), the University of Texas (TAMU), the Eckerd College, the Centro de Investigaciones Marinas de La Universidad de La Habana (CIM-UH) and the Centro de Estudios Ambientales de Cienfuegos (CEAC) of the Ministerio de Ciencia,

Tecnología y Medioambiente. Sediment samples were collected in seven stations at 1296–1670 m using a multi-corer in the area between Havana and the Cape of San Antonio from 2017-05-13 to 2017-05-23. Molluscs (most of them empty shells) from the top 10 cm of each core were sieved through a 0.5 mm screen, and then separated with a stereomicroscope. Scanning electron micrographs were taken at Centro de apoyo Científico y Tecnológico a la investigación (CaCTi) of the University of Vigo on a FEI Quanta 200 microscope, following standard methods for scanning electron microscopy. The terminology of shell characters follows GEIGER (2012).

Abbreviations:

MNCN, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid, Spain.

SYSTEMATICS

Class GASTROPODA Cuvier, 1795
Subclass VETIGASTROPODA Salvini-Plawen, 1980
Family SCISSURELLIDAE Gray, 1847
Genus *Scissurella* d'Orbigny, 1824

Type species: *Scissurella laeovigata* d'Orbigny, 1824 [= *S. costata* d'Orbigny, 1824] by subsequent designation of Gray, (1847).

Scissurella enriquevidali n. sp. (Figure 1)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:45341F36-5761-414F-BC29-A38B1CC60167

Type material. *Holotype*: Cuba • 1 shell (Fig. 1A-B, F-G); off Cayo Jutías; 22° 48.0936'N, 84° 06.7136'W; 1296 m depth; 20 May 2017; WEATHERBIRD II 2017 sta. SL39; MNCN15.05/200133H. *Paratype*: • 1 shell (Fig. 1C-E); same data as for holotype; MNCN15.05/200133P.

Type locality: off Cayo Jutías, NW Cuba, 22° 48.0936'N, 84° 06.7136'W, 1296 m depth.

Etymology: The specific name honours Enrique Vidal, founding member of the Spanish Malacological Society (Sociedad Española de Malacología).

Description (holotype): Shell minute (holotype diameter, 0.76 mm, Fig. 1A, B; paratype diameter 0.94 mm, Fig. 1C, D), trochiform, spire sunken in. Protoconch of 1 whorl, diameter 180 µm, with flocculent sculpture, apertural varix connecting to embryonic cap, apertural margin slightly convex (Fig. 1E-G). Teleoconch I of 1 whorl, spiral cord in position

of selenizone, first half whorl without axial sculpture, second half with 11–12 axial lamellae of increasing distinctness, crossing the spiral cord and fading towards suture. Teleoconch II of 0.7 whorl (holotype) to 1 whorl (paratype), suture strongly impressed. Shoulder with 19 (holotype) and 25 (paratype) axial lamellae not reaching the periphery, interstices

Figure 1. *Scissurella enriquevidali* n. sp. Off Cayo Jutías, NW Cuba, 22° 48.0936' N, 84° 06.7136' W, 1296 m. A, B: holotype, diameter 0.76 mm (MNCN15.05/200133H); C, D: paratype, diameter 0.94 mm (MNCN15.05/200133P); E: protoconch of paratype; F, G: protoconch and detail of protoconch microsculpture of the holotype.

Figura 1. Scissurella enriquevidali n. sp. Cayo Jutías, NW Cuba, 22° 48.0936'N, 84° 06.7136'W, 1296 m. A, B: holotipo, diámetro 0,76 mm (MNCN15.05/200133H); C, D: paratipo, diámetro 0,94 mm (MNCN15.05/200133P); E: protoconcha del paratipo; F, G: protoconcha y detalle de la microescultura de la protoconcha del holotipo.

with fine growth lines, no spiral sculpture in holotype; paratype with fine spiral lines on outer half of shoulder, first after 0.1 teleoconch II whorls, increasing to four at broken apertural margin. Base with constriction below selenizone, axial lamellae of same strength and density as on shoulder (36 in last whorl of paratype), fading towards umbilicus, two spiral cords on last whorl, the second one starting after 0.3 teleoconch II whorls. Umbilicus wide, underside of protoconch visible. Selenizone above periphery, keels moderately strong, elevated, with low and spaced lunules; slit open, margins parallel. Animal unknown.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality.

Remarks: *Scissurella Enriquevidali* n. sp. differs from all other known species of the genus by its unusual protoconch and shell characters. It is placed in the genus *Scissurella* and not considered a juvenile *Sinezona* or *Satondella* since both specimens are almost fully-grown (especially the paratype). A typical sign of maturation in scissurellids is the descent of the apertural margin along the coiling of the shell on the last quarter whorl, which is evident in both specimens. The margins of the selenizone remain perfectly parallel, while in *Sinezona* or *Satondella*, specimens reaching maturity show converging margins of the selenizone to eventually form the diagnostic foramen.

The present species is amongst the smaller scissurellids, yet within the known range of adult *Scissurella* species [e.g., *S. azorensis* Nolt, 2008: 0.75 mm, *S. kaiserae* Geiger, 2006: 0.6 mm, *S. lobini* (Burnay & Rolán, 1990): 0.65 mm, *S. maraisorum* Geiger, 2006: 0.72 mm, *S. phenax* Geiger, 2012: 0.7 mm, *S. redferni* (Rolán, 1996): 0.65 mm, *S. skeneoides* Geiger, 2012: 0.72 mm].

The flocculent protoconch sculpture while frequently found in Anatomidae is uncommon amongst scissurellids. It is known from *Scissurella morretesi* Montouchet, 1972 from Brazil, *S. clathrata* Strebel, 1908 from cold-temperate South

America, and the Indo-Pacific *Sinezona macleani* Geiger, 2006. The most frequent protoconch sculpture in scissurellids are weak and strong axial cords, with select species showing different morphologies, such as smooth [*S. alto* Geiger, 2003; *S. cebuana* Bandel, 1998; *S. xandaros* Geiger, 2012; *Sinezona ferriezi* (Crosse, 1867), *Sinezona singeri* Geiger, 2006)] or with spiral lines [*Sinezona globosa*, Geiger, 2006, *Sinezona plicata* (Hedley, 1899)]. Flocculent or microgranular protoconch sculpture should not be confused with eroded protoconchs as discussed elsewhere (GEIGER, 2012: fig. 19). The type specimens of *Scissurella Enriquevidali* both have very well-preserved protoconch with clean apertural margin, intact apertural varix, and well-structured protoconch surface. The flocculent sculpture is not a preservation or recrystallization artifact, nor due to surface erosion or abrasion, but the native state of the species.

The protoconch sculpture of *S. Enriquevidali* n. sp. does not assist with the placement in any of the scissurellid genera. Its flocculent sculpture is not found in the type species of *Scissurella* (*S. laevigata* d'Orbigny, 1824 [= *S. costata* d'Orbigny, 1824]: fine axials) nor in that of *Sinezona* (*Schismope brevis* Hedley, 1904: strong axials) (GEIGER, 2012). Furthermore, protoconch sculpture has been shown to be phylogenetically uninformative (GEIGER, 2003).

The overall trochoid-depressed morphology with sunken in apex is also shared with a few *Scissurella* species. *Scissurella redferni* from the Caribbean, the Panamic *S. kaiserae*, *S. lobini* from the Cape Verde Islands, the eastern South African *S. maraisorum*, and *S. prendrevillei* Powell, 1933 from New Zealand, all have a protoconch with strong axial cords, lack a spiral in the position of the selenizone on teleoconch I, and have strong microlamellae between the axial cords on the teleoconch. *Scissurella regalis* Geiger & Marshall, 2012 from New Zealand has a protoconch with fine axial cords and distinctly raised axial lamellae on the teleoconch.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank to crews and scientific staff of cruise WB0517 of the R/V WEATHERBIRD II for collecting the samples used in this study, and specially to the campaign director Dr. Steven A. Murawski (USF) and Dr.

Maickel Armenteros Almanza (CIM-UH). Jesús Méndez and Inés Pazos from Centro de Apoyo Científico y Tecnológico a la Investigación (CACTI) of the Universidad de Vigo are acknowledged for SEM images.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ARMENTEROS M. 2019. *Mollusk and meiofauna communities data collected on board the R/V Weatherbird II cruise WB0517 in the northwestern margin of Cuba from 2017-05-13 to 2017-05-23*. Distributed by: Gulf of Mexico Research Initiative Information and Data Cooperative (GRIIDC), Harte Research Institute, Texas A&M University–Corpus Christi. doi: 10.7266/n7-88ne-3229. <https://data.gulfresearchinitiative.org/data/R6.x805.000:0065#distributionInfo> [Accessed 10/03/2021].
- ESPINOSA J. 2006. *Moluscos - Filo MOLLUSCA. Lista de especies registradas para Cuba*. Instituto de Oceanología, La Habana, 44 pp. In Claro, R. (Ed.): *La Biodiversidad marina de Cuba*. <http://repositorio.geotech.cu/jspui/bitstream/1234/1397/89/071%20Lista%20de%20Moluscos%20-%20Cuba.pdf>. [Accessed 21/05/2021].
- ESPINOSA J., FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS R. & ROLÁN E. 1995. Catálogo actualizado de los moluscos marinos actuales de Cuba. *Reseñas Malacológicas*, 9: 1-90.
- FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS R., RUBIO F. & ROLÁN E. 2018a. A new species of the genus *Brookula* (Gastropoda, Seguenzioidea) from deep water of Cuba. *Iberus*, 36 (1): 55-59.
- FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS R., RUBIO F. & ROLÁN E. 2018b. A new species of the genus *Neusas* (Gastropoda: Tornidae) from deep water of Cuba. *Gloria Maris*, 57 (2): 64-66.
- FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS R., RUBIO F. & ROLÁN E. 2019a. A new species of the genus *Emiliotia* (Gastropoda, Trochoidea) from deep water of Cuba. *Iberus*, 37 (2): 243-247.
- FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS R., RUBIO F. & ROLÁN R. 2019b. Three new species of the genus *Adeuomphalus* (Gastropoda: Seguenzioidea) from deep water of Cuba. *Gloria Maris*, 58 (1): 3-9.
- FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS R., RUBIO F. & ROLÁN E. 2019c. A new species of the genus *Ventsia* (Gastropoda, Seguenzioidea) from deep water of Cuba. *Gloria Maris*, 58 (1): 23-25.
- FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS R., RUBIO F. & ROLÁN E. 2019d. A new species of the genus *Lyocyclus* (Gastropoda: Caenogastropoda) from deep water of Cuba. *Gloria Maris*, 58 (3): 109-112.
- GEIGER D.L. 2003. Phylogenetic assessment of characters proposed for the generic classification of Recent Scissurellidae (Gastropoda: Vetigastropoda) with a description of one new genus and six new species from Easter Island and Australia. *Molluscan Research*, 23: 21-83.
- GEIGER D.L. 2012. *Monograph of the little slit shells. Volume 1. Introduction, Scissurellidae. Volume 2. Anatomidae, Larocheidae, Depressizonidae, Sutilizonidae, Temnocinclidae*. Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History Monographs, 7, vol. 1 pp. 1-728, vol. 2 pp. 729-1291.